

Symmetries in Simple Harmonic Motion and Their Applications

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1 Abstract

The Simple Harmonic motion is ubiquitous in nature at every scale from macroscopic bodies to the very microscopic elementary particles like electrons and photons. In the usual macroscopic scales motion of particles obey Newtonian and Relativistic dynamics which is modeled very accurately by linear Mathematics developed over the last few centuries. But at the quantum scales we inherently have to deal with probabilities and the wave particle dual nature becomes apparent at microscopic scales. To describe the energy of photons in Quantum Field Theory we have to use the notion of frequency which is a Simple Harmonic Motion Notion which in turn requires Sines and Cosines. In this Paper I would like to formulate a Mathematical Model by generalizing some symmetry principles from Simple Harmonic motion and show how this Model reduces to linear Mathematics at high frequencies or longer time scales and how this model maybe useful in general for quantum physicists in particular for dealing with infinities.

2 Revisiting Simple Harmonic Motion

Let the frequency of a particle executing Simple Harmonic motion be 1 oscillation per 2π time units. Let the particle start at $t = 0$ units at $x = 1$ and say at $t = \pi$ units completes half cycle at $x = -1$ at a particular instant of time from $[0, \pi]$ the position of the particle is given by the equation $\cos(t)$. For this part of the journey we note some symmetries between the position of the particle as it runs on a linear path from $x = 1$ to $x = -1$ and the variable of time 't' which can be imagined to lie on a semicircle during this journey. The length of the total linear path covered by the particle during at any instant t in $[0, \pi]$ is given by $l(t) = 1 - \cos(t)$ and the length of the semicircular path covered by the 'time' variable is t. There is a symmetry between $l(t)$ and the variable 't' in that they both cover exactly 0 fraction at 0 second, both covers half fraction at time $t = \pi/2$ and they both cover full fraction of their total length at $t = \pi$. These three points in time are the only points where the

relative fraction of total path length traversed by these two variables ‘ $l(t)$ ’ and ‘ t ’ are equal in the interval considered.

The fundamental motivation for the Mathematical Model formulated throughout the paper is that the fundamental effect of time in Universe at each scale is kind of the above example $l(t)$ in that since we cannot directly observe time we model mathematically functions of $l(t)$ exclusively since it is the only observable effect of the most ubiquitous system at every scale in nature. For large time scales functions of $l(t)$ and corresponding functions of $(2t/\pi)$ behave very similarly and linearly and making this precise will be a central result of the paper. A key feature of the above example is that at time $t=0$ the effect of time is not instantaneous and $l(t)$ derivative at $t = 0$ is zero in other words it took some time for the effect of time to show up whereas in mathematics usually when we talk about functions say $f(t) = t$ the effect of time is instantaneous, removing this will be a key feature of the mathematical model.

3 Mathematical Model

To work with full generality we make no presumptions about the variables but for most cases ‘ x ’ will be used for the time and space variables. We use modulo arithmetic for real numbers in formulas.

The general scheme for building functions I am going to use is building functions from functions whose derivatives are continuous and are only sines or only cosines of a single frequency after that we will generalize to combination of functions with multiple frequencies.

3.1 Functions whose derivatives are only sinusoidal

Lets consider a particular class of functions whose derivatives are continuous and sinusoidal in form of one frequency at a time. (Frequency is conventionally taken to be the coefficient of x in sine and is 1 in this case)

One such function is :

$$f(x) = 2x/\pi + 1 - \cos(\text{mod}(x, \pi)) - \text{mod}(2x/\pi, 2)$$

Its derivative is always a continuous sinusoidal of frequency 1. One way to imagine this is to consider a particle undergoing Simple Harmonic Motion from $x = 0$ to $x = 2$ and the moment it reaches $x = 2$ we disconnect the spring and attach its center from $x = 1$ to $x = 3$ and so the particle will look like moving forward in a simple harmonic way this already shows functions of these types at least in principle can represent systems showing both wave particle duality while showing space itself might have some inherent harmonic structure. For me there are two ways to look at the discontinuity of second derivatives at $n\pi$ one is to accept that mathematically it is the way it is. Second is to consider that π to 2π is equivalent to π to 0 which is negative to the direction 0 to π and rationalize this way. (Please note this is just a heuristic).

3.2 Mathematical Results

Now I present the central result of the paper.

Theorem 1.1

Let $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be the function

$$f(x) = 2x/\pi$$

Consider a sequence of functions $f_n : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $n \geq 1$ whose derivatives are continuous and sinusoidal and the functions are of the form :

$$f_n(x) = 2x/\pi + \frac{1}{n}(1 - \cos(\text{mod}(nx, \pi))) - \text{mod}(2x/\pi, 2/n)$$

Claim: The sequence of functions f_n converges uniformly to f on \mathbb{R}

Proof:

Let $\epsilon > 0$

Since the difference function $f(x) - f_n(x)$ is periodic with period π/n . It suffices to check the maximum numerical distance in the interval $[0, \pi/n]$.

From symmetry of line and circle we consider the maximum distance from 0 to $\pi/2n$.

The distance function $d_n : [0, \pi/2n] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $d_n(x) = 2x/\pi - 1/n + \frac{1}{n}\cos nx$.

Since $d_n''(x) \leq 0$ from 0 to $\pi/2n$ and $d_n(0) = d_n(\pi/2n) = 0$

Therefore, from second derivative test $\|f_n - f\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} |f(x) - f_n(x)| = d_n(x_n)$ where for all $n \geq 1$, x_n is defined as the point from $[0, \pi/2n]$ at which $d_n'(x_n) = 0$

$$d_n'(x) = 2/\pi - \sin(nx)$$

$$d_n'(x_n) = 0 \implies x_n = (1/n)\arcsin(2/\pi)$$

$$d_n(x_n) = 2(\arcsin(2/\pi))/n\pi - 1/n + (1/n)\cos(\arcsin(2/\pi))$$

$$d_n(x_n) = (1/n)[2(\arcsin(2/\pi))/\pi - 1 + \sqrt{1 - (2/\pi)^2}]$$

We observe this is a strictly decreasing function in n and also $d_n(x_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Therefore there exist $N \geq 1$ such that $\forall n \geq N$ $d_n(x_n) < \epsilon$

Since $\|f_n - f\|_\infty = d_n(x_n)$

Therefore f_n converges uniformly to f and hence we conclude the proof.

Corollary 1.2 Let $N \geq 1$ and $f, f_n : [-N\pi, N\pi] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be restricted on a compact domain and g be a continuous function on \mathbb{R} then $g(f_n)$ converges uniformly to $g(f)$ on $[-N\pi, N\pi]$.

Corollary 1.3 Let $N \geq 1$ and $f, f_n : [-N\pi, N\pi] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be restricted on a compact domain and g be a continuous function on \mathbb{R} then $\int_a^b g(f_n(x)) dx$

converges to $\int_a^b g(2x/\pi) dx \forall a, b$ in $[-N\pi, N\pi]$.

Some remarks about the proof are is that the proof essentially depends only on one interval of $[0, \pi/n]$ to demonstrate uniform convergence over whole of \mathbb{R} and is essentially a scaling proof in the sense that given any frequency with large time scales with respect to frequency convergence will become apparent and experimentally since for macroscopic object the debroglie frequency is very high compared to modern experimental instruments detection is difficult(1kg mass at rest has frequency of the order of $10^{50} Hz$ far greater than what our modern tools can reach).It would also be convenient further to extend domains of *arcsin* , *arccos* using real modulo arithmetic.At high frequencies when we experimentally measure a particle velocity we are mathematically taking average between two points which for physics maybe small but in math can contain very high number of periods which makes experimentally very difficult to distinguish between these two models.

3.3 Generalities

The ideas developed can be extended into complex analysis and geometry. I will briefly touch upon them as this is not the focus of this paper.

For example take the curve $(2x/\pi)^2 + (2y/\pi)^2 = r^2$ The analogous curve for frequency one would be :

Take $f(x) = 2x/\pi + 1 - \cos(\text{mod}(x, \pi)) - \text{mod}(2x/\pi, 2)$

and $g(y) = 2y/\pi + 1 - \cos(\text{mod}(y, \pi)) - \text{mod}(2y/\pi, 2)$

Then corresponding to above circle the equation would be

$$f(x)^2 + g(y)^2 = r^2$$

and again the convergence between these curves becomes apparent as r becomes large relative to π . This idea can be extended to other general continuous curves in 2 and higher dimensions and for other continuous frequencies as well.

For $f(x) = 2x/\pi$ let $a > 0$ be a real number and represent the frequency. The corresponding function will be

$$f_a(x) = 2x/\pi + \frac{1}{a}(1 - \cos(\text{mod}(ax, \pi))) - \text{mod}(2x/\pi, 2/a)$$

For complex analysis again corresponding to each $x + iy$ we have for each positive real frequency $a > 0$.

Define

$$f_a(x) = x + \frac{1}{a}(1 - \cos(\text{mod}(a\pi x/2, \pi))) - \text{mod}(x, 2/a)$$

Corresponding to $x + iy$ would be the complex number $f_a(x) + if_a(y)$ and again we can analyze their continuous functions.

In place of *cos* we could have used *sine* and performed a similar treatment. I will just give the formula for one case of frequency one for $f(x) = 2x/\pi$ the corresponding sine function whose derivative is of the form cosine.

$$g(x) = 2x/\pi + \sin(\text{mod}(x, \pi/2)) - \text{mod}(2x/\pi, 1)$$

$\forall x$ satisfying $(\text{mod}(x, \pi) = \text{mod}(x, \pi/2))$

$$g(x) = 2x/\pi + \sin(\text{mod}(x, -\pi/2)) - \text{mod}(2x/\pi, -1)$$

$\forall x$ satisfying $(\text{mod}(x, \pi) > \text{mod}(x, \pi/2))$

By taking linear combinations of these two fundamental functions at various frequencies one can get another rich source of functions which have derivatives linear combinations of purely harmonic functions sine and cosine.

3.4 Derivative Structure

The following result maybe of use to quantum physicists dealing with infinities due to a regular derivative structure of the functions.

Corollary 1.4

Let $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be the function

$$f(x) = 2x/\pi$$

and let $f_n : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be the functions

$$f_n(x) = 2x/\pi + \frac{1}{n}(1 - \cos(\text{mod}(nx, \pi))) - \text{mod}(2x/\pi, 2/n)$$

Let $g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable function on \mathbb{R}

Fix $n \geq 1$

Let N be any integer and consider the interval $[N\pi/n, (N+1)\pi/n]$

Then $g(f(x)) = g(f_n(x))$ for at least three values at $N\pi/n, N\pi/n + \pi/2n$ and $N\pi/n + \pi/n$ and the derivative of $g(f_n)$ is zero at $N\pi/n$ and $N\pi/n + \pi/n$ by chain rule since the derivative of f_n is purely sinusoidal and is evaluated at multiple of π .

This result gives a nice harmonic structure on the derivatives and solves the instantaneous effect of time difficulty and no matter how high the frequency or how fast the function is this result is still valid while preserving the value of function for at least three points in the interval. Studying general derivative behavior of these functions may be of use to quantum physicists. In particular because polylogarithm functions are used in some QED calculations and the indefinite integral of $x/\cos x$ involves polylogarithm functions pointing this model might be more appropriate at those scales.

3.5 Mathematical Modeling for Quantum Systems

Since the area under curve is same for $2x/\pi$ and f_n for any one particular period of π/n and due to the convergence results shown above, the mathematical model developed above can better suit to study quantum mechanical systems due to the division in pieces for every periods of π/n this idea can be generalized to other physical variables also and is naturally suited for quantization and physical systems at low time and length scales.

3.6 General Mathematical Construction

The above analysis is a special case for constructing and combining functions whose derivatives are continuous and purely sinusoidal or cosinusoidal. The functions we considered above had fixed frequency and amplitude and were increasing, although it is this restriction that allowed easily to get the closed form formulas for the functions. Now I present the general construction where these restrictions are removed.

Lets first fix a frequency of 1 and consider the functions:

$$f_n(x) = (2n + 1) \pm \cos x$$

At the end of every period of length π we have two options either to stay on the same branch or move upwards or downwards along the y -axis, the main reason such construction works mathematically is due to the fact that these curves intersections are precisely the points where the derivatives are zero in which case the constants of integration starts interacting with one another.

We do not have to consider single frequency and can combine multiple frequencies. For example start at branch $1 - \cos x$ at $x=0$ stay there until $x = \pi$ at which $y = 2$ then climb on the higher frequency branch $3 - \cos 2x$ stay in this branch till 7π at which $y = 2$ and finally climb down the branch at 7π to the original branch $1 - \cos x$.

By varying amplitudes, frequencies, and phase shifts we can combine such functions by the same above mathematical construction and the above mathematical phenomenon is very similar to the physical phenomena of an electron getting excited from a low energy (low frequency) state to a high energy (high frequency) staying there for a few time (few oscillations) and finally de exciting (climbing down the branch) back to the original state (starting branch). The sequence of functions obtained in Theorem 1.1 can be used to get for any real continuous function $g(x)$ at any particular value x a sequence of numbers which converges pointwise at x analogous to a Taylor series approximation with purely harmonic functions of single frequency at a time. I conclude with this the discussion of the mathematical model.

4 A simple harmonic motion heuristic

Consider a particle of mass 1 undergoing simple harmonic motion with spring constant k let the maximum amplitude be denoted by A_0 , its energy is given by $(1/2)kA_0^2$ and let $2\pi f_0$ denote the natural frequency $= \sqrt{k}$.

Let us suppose this energy is fixed and the particle moves in 1d abstractly in space retaining its oscillating identity and due to the wave character of the particle it creates a standing wave profile whose amplitudes in space in the x direction is given by the profile $A(x) = 2A_0 \sin((2\pi/b)x)$ for some wavelength b .

Energy of a particle in this region at a particular x will be given as $(1/2)k'A(x)^2$ where k' is the apparent spring constant at x applying energy conservation $((1/2)kA_0^2) = ((1/2)k'A(x)^2)$ which implies $k/k' = 4\sin^2((2\pi/b)x)$

since $\sqrt{k} = 2\pi f$ the ratio of frequencies $f_0/f' = \sqrt{k_0/k} = |2\sin((2\pi/b)x)|$ which gives the time distribution over x as $\Delta t \propto |2\sin((2\pi/b)x)|\Delta x$

(This intuition is built on the fact that when we consider a wave on a string when waves are traveling forward the energy is transported uniformly in the forward direction but when a standing wave is formed there occurs a distribution in energy in regions of space but frequency remains uniform in space, this is reversed in the above example for a single particle and the energy is now constant but the time spent in various regions is now different and we expect the particle to spend 0 time at 0 energy regions (nodes), low time in the low energy regions barely oscillating at the ends and most time in between and the exact distribution is which we got by applying energy conservation).

4.1 Photon heuristic

Continuing with the above analogy for electromagnetic wave set the frequency of a photon to f_0 oscillation per 1 time unit

Energy of electric field is related to its magnitude square (E_0^2) and so considering this we may assume a form for the Planck's constant to be as $h=cA_0^2$ for some constant c and hence the energy equation of a photon becomes $E=cA_0^2 f$ again let the photon interfere and say an amplitude profile $A(x) = 2A_0 \sin(2\pi x/\lambda)$ is formed for wavelength λ .

Let the apparent frequency at x be f' . Again by applying energy conservation we get $cA_0^2 f_0 = cA(x)^2 f'$ thus $f_0/f' = 4\sin^2(2\pi x/\lambda)$ which gives the time distribution over x as $\Delta t \propto 4\sin^2((2\pi/\lambda)x)\Delta x$.

In double slit experiment with single photons at a time the usual way to explain the observed pattern is to take two point sources in phase and see the resulting wave at a point on screen by algebraic sum and when we sum two E fields we get the resultant composed of two parts one is the amplitude and the other is the time varying sinusoidal oscillation. It seems more natural to think that the resultant geometry is a consequence of pure geometry because if we take

both signals traveling at same speed c the very first incidence will happen at different times but if we see this phenomenon as a result of pure geometry we can take the amplitude to be simply proportional to $(\cos(x_1) + \cos(x_2))^2 + (\sin(x_1) + \sin(x_2))^2$ and appropriate normalization where x_1 and x_2 are the path lengths of First and Second sources respectively and the above sum does not depend on the initial phase, this method can be generalized to more than 2 slits or continuous integral also.

Generalizing this idea to the double slit experiment with single photon may reproduce the experimentally observed data. One possible way to rationalize this is take a single photon of a well defined frequency moving in z direction incident at a single slit now the probability is high at the center and low as we move away from center this can be understood by applying momentum and energy conservation simultaneously to get $cA_0^2 f_0 = cA(x)^2 f'$ where x denotes the position of detected photon as the photon is detected away from center it's momentum along z direction is decreased also decreasing the amplitude we consider for energy conservation hence we finally get $cA_0^2 f_0 = cA_0^2 (p_z(x)/p_0)^2 f'$ where p_0 is the initial momentum before hitting the slit thereby giving the time distribution as $\Delta t \propto (p_z/p_0)^2 \Delta z$. The main idea is to write t as a function of position of particle and apply these energy and momentum conservation principles to find the exact time and position of particles with the understanding that the time spent at one location is proportional to the amplitude at that location. This method may be generalized to other particles and I hope this can give an alternative description of particles.

Appendix:Mathematical Investigations into Modular Calculus

From above arguments it appears to truly mathematically model the dual nature of particles as a single unified mathematical concept we need to model in pure mathematics the concept of real line (the linear structure) with added structure of periodicity using real modulo arithmetic (which at least in pure mathematics is not investigated at all) of course the starting point will be the equivalence relations.

Let \mathbb{R} denote the set of real numbers and let $a > 0$ be any positive real number. Define a relation \sim on \mathbb{R} such that $x \sim y$ iff $|x - y| \pmod{a} = 0$. It is easy to check that this relation is an equivalence relation on \mathbb{R} and hence partitions the set of real numbers into disjoint equivalence classes $[x_i]$ for $i \in [0, a)$ where $x_i = i$.

$$\bigcup_{i \in [0, a)} [x_i] = \mathbb{R}$$

$$\begin{aligned} [x_i] \cap [x_j] &= \phi, \quad \forall i \neq j & i, j \in [0, a) \\ [x_i] \cap [x_j] &= [x_i], \quad \forall i = j & i, j \in [0, a) \end{aligned}$$

With this basic framework set we may develop a more rigorous mathematical theory of modular calculus where the ordinary real line is given an added robust periodic structure and which mathematically allows for every point in \mathbb{R} to talk about sines and cosines of each point simultaneously with it's linear euclidean numerical coordinate in a coherent canonical manner.

Representation of Basic Trigonometric Functions

The complex number e^{ix} has a structurally rich structure combining both $\sin x$ and $\cos x$ in an algebraic form by using i .

Taking the analogy of right angle in cartesian coordinates it represents a canonical choice to describe and do Mathematics of functions . The right angle has the specialty that take any random line in 2-D Plane extended up to infinity and take any point and call it the origin for every other line there exist another symmetric line except for the line at right angle where the two symmetric lines coincide. Same thing happens for a circle in 2D with positive X,Y axes and a quarter circle the line $y=x$ is doing a similar role played by the right angle exploiting the symmetry. This suggests a more natural and canonical way to define the basic trigonometric functions maybe to define as follows:

$$SIN(x) = \sin(x + \pi/4) = (1/\sqrt{2})(\cos x + \sin x)$$

$$COS(x) = \cos(x + \pi/4) = (1/\sqrt{2})(\cos x - \sin x)$$

The symmetry at $\pi/4$ ($y = x$) helps to take advantage of the richness in algebraic structure and does not prefer X or Y axes for definition.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

5 References

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